

Repurposing of chlorpromazine in COVID-19 treatment: the reCoVery study

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Introduction

The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic comprises a total of more than 2 588 000 cases and 182 800 deaths (1). It is the third and most severe coronavirus epidemic after SARS-CoV-1 in 2003 and MERS-CoV in 2012. The interest in anticoronavirus drug development has been limited so far and effective methods to prevent or treat coronavirus infections in humans are still lacking. Since the beginning of the COVID-19 outbreak several weeks ago, we observe in Sainte-Anne hospital (Paris, France) a lower prevalence of symptomatic and severe forms of COVID-19 infections in psychiatric patients (~4%) compared to health care professionals (~14%). Similar observations have been noted in other psychiatric units in France, China, Italy and Spain. Our hypothesis is that psychiatric patients could be protected from the virulent form of COVID-19 the psychotropic treatment that they are receiving.

Chlorpromazine (CPZ) is a phenothiazine derivative widely used in clinical routine in the treatment of acute and chronic psychoses. This first antipsychotic medication has been discovered in 1952 by Delay and Deniker (2) at Sainte-Anne hospital. In addition to its antipsychotic effects, several in vitro studies have also demonstrated a CPZ antiviral activity via the inhibition of clathrin-dependent endocytosis (3,4). These antiviral properties were found efficient against hepatitis viruses (5), alphaviruses (6), bronchitis-virus (7) and MHV-2 (8). Recently, independent studies revealed that CPZ was also an anti-MERS-CoV and an anti-SARS-CoV-1 drug (9–11). In comparison to other antiviral drugs, the main advantages of CPZ lie in its biodistribution: (1) CPZ is known to cross the blood-brain barrier (12) and could therefore prevent the neurological forms of COVID-19 ; (2) CPZ is highly concentrated in saliva and could therefore reduce the contagiousness of COVID-19 since its concentrations in saliva is 4-50 times higher than in plasma (13).

Urgent action is needed to fight this fatal coronavirus infection by reducing the number of infected people along with the infection contagiousness and severity. The repositioning of CPZ holds promise for anti-SARS-CoV-2 activity and offers an alternative and rapid strategy to

alleviate the virus propagation and the infection severity and lethality. This CPZ repositioning strategy avoids numerous developmental and experimental steps, saves precious time to rapidly establish an anti-COVID-19 therapy with well-known, limited and easy to manage side effects. Indeed, CPZ is a FDA-approved drug with an excellent tolerance profile, prescribed for around 70 years, in psychiatry but also in clinical routine in nausea and vomiting of pregnancy (14), in advanced cancer (15), and also to treat headaches in various neurological conditions (16–18).

Our clinical study aims at testing the efficacy of CPZ as anti-COVID-19 treatment. Our consortium brings together worldwide recognized experts in the fields of infectious diseases, virology, as well as psychiatrists that are experts in the development and use of psychotropic drugs.

Methods

reCoVery is a multicentric single blind randomized pilot clinical trial whose main objective is to compare the efficacy of the standard-of-care (SOC) treatment *versus* SOC + CPZ treatment in patients infected by COVID-19 with respiratory symptoms and requiring hospitalization. The efficacy evaluation will be based on clinical, biological and radiological criteria over a total period of 28 days.

The secondary objectives are five-folds:

- A. demonstrate a clinical improvement with CPZ + SOC versus SOC at different time points between D1 and D28
- B. demonstrate a viral improvement (PCR, viral load) with CPZ + SOC versus SOC at different time points between D1 and D28
- C. demonstrate an inflammatory improvement with CPZ + SOC versus SOC at different time points between D1 and D28
- D. demonstrate a pulmonary parenchymal improvement (chest CT) with CPZ + SOC versus SOC between D1 and D7
- E. define the optimal dose of CPZ and evaluate its tolerance.

Main and secondary objectives include those recommended by WHO 2020 COVID-19 guidelines (19).

Conclusion

The originality of the reCoVery study is based on the repositioning of CPZ, a well-known drug with antiviral properties and excellent tolerance profile, to treat the actual covid-19 pandemic for which effective treatments are still unknown. The potential therapeutic benefit of CPZ

against COVID-19 is based on both basic and epidemiological evidences : 1) the established in vitro antiviral properties at low doses against coronaviruses MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-1 via the inhibition of clathrin-dependent endocytosis essential for the entry of the coronavirus into the cells ; and 2) the observation in several psychiatric units of low spread of symptomatic forms of COVID-19 among patients receiving CPZ treatments.

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